

Development and Evaluation of Nut-Based Probiotic Yogurt Alternative to Dairy Ferments

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Abstract

The growing incidence of lactose intolerance, dairy allergies, and the global shift toward plant-based diets have accelerated the demand for non-dairy probiotic foods. This study investigates the formulation, fermentation, and nutritional evaluation of nut-based yogurt using cashews, almonds, and coconut milk. Three formulations (T₁, T₂, T₃) were developed and subjected to sensory, nutritional, microbial and statistical analysis. T₂, composed of 50% coconut milk, 15% almonds, 25% cashews and 10% other ingredients, exhibited the highest overall acceptability (6.7 ± 0.42) across sensory parameters. Nutritional analysis of the best-performing sample showed 9.2 g/100g protein, 15.7 g/100g carbohydrates, 23.5 g/100g fat, 2.7 g/100g dietary fiber and 48.6% moisture content. Vitamin and mineral content included 5.2 mg/100g iron, 76 mg/100g calcium, 3.45 mg/100g vitamin A and 13.3 mg/100g vitamin C. Microbial testing confirmed the product's safety with aerobic plate counts and yeast/mold levels <10 CFU/g and the absence of pathogens such as *Enterobacteriaceae* and *S. aureus*. Statistical analysis via one-way ANOVA revealed no significant difference among the three formulations at the 5% level ($p = 0.02$). This research confirms that nut-based yogurt, particularly the T₂ formulation, presents a viable, nutritious, and safe alternative to conventional dairy yogurts, with potential applications in the functional food sector.

Keywords: Nut-based yogurt, Dairy-free fermentation, Plant-based probiotics, Functional foods, Sensory evaluation, Vegan dairy alternatives

1. Introduction

In recent decades, global dietary preferences have shifted significantly due to increasing awareness surrounding health, sustainability, and ethical considerations. The rise in plant-based food consumption is fueled not only by ethical and environmental concerns but also by the increasing prevalence of lactose intolerance, cow's milk protein allergy and other gastrointestinal disorders linked to dairy intake (Granato *et al.*, 2010; Shori, 2013) ^[6, 10]. This growing demand for dairy-free alternatives has catalyzed innovation in functional foods, particularly those replicating the sensory and nutritional benefits of traditional dairy products. Among the emerging alternatives, plant-based yogurts have garnered substantial attention due to their ability to incorporate probiotic cultures traditionally associated with dairy fermentation. Within this category, nut-based yogurts-produced from cashews, almonds, and macadamias-offer a unique balance of nutritional richness and favorable organoleptic properties (Makinen *et al.*, 2016) ^[7]. These nuts

are naturally high in unsaturated fats, plant-based proteins and micronutrients such as magnesium, zinc, and vitamin E, positioning them as ideal bases for developing functional fermented foods.

Cashews, in particular, are known for their creamy consistency and mild flavor, which facilitate textural and flavor compatibility with probiotic fermentation. Almonds contribute both nutritional diversity and functional fiber content, while coconut milk adds body and a subtle natural sweetness, further enhancing the appeal of the final product. When fermented with lactic acid bacteria such as *Lactobacillus* and *Bifid bacterium* spp., these plant matrices can support microbial growth, develop desirable tanginess, and contribute to gut microbiota modulation (Rinaldi *et al.*, 2020) ^[9].

Probiotics play a vital role in enhancing human health through mechanisms such as modulation of intestinal microbiota, improved lactose metabolism, and strengthening of immune function. Incorporating these live cultures into

non-dairy substrates, however, presents technological challenges. Factors such as nutrient availability, pH buffering capacity, and matrix stability all influence probiotic viability and product acceptability (Granato *et al.*, 2010) [6]. Overcoming these challenges requires careful formulation and processing, particularly in homemade or small-scale settings where precision may vary.

Existing research has focused on soy, oat, or rice-based yogurt alternatives, while nut-based substrates remain relatively underexplored in the scientific literature. Moreover, there is a lack of comprehensive studies that combine formulation, sensory evaluation, nutritional profiling and microbial safety of such products. Given the increasing market demand and the health potential of these dairy-free fermented foods, further empirical investigation is warranted. Although nut-based yogurt alternatives are commercially available, there is a paucity of standardized, scientifically validated protocols that evaluate their formulation, sensory quality, microbial safety and nutritional efficacy in an integrated manner. Hence the study was framed to Develop and Evaluate a Probiotic-Rich, Nut-based Yogurt using Almonds, Cashews and coconut milk; to assess its sensory acceptability, nutritional value and microbiological safety.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Ingredient Procurement

Raw nuts including Cashew Nuts (*Anacardium occidentale*) and almonds (*Prunus dulcis*) were procured from a certified organic food supplier in Hyderabad, India. Coconut milk (CM) was obtained from a local market (100% natural, preservative-free). Probiotic capsules containing a minimum of 10 billion CFU per capsule, comprising strains of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Bifidobacterium bifidum*, were purchased from a commercial supplier (Certified vegan, dairy-free). Additional ingredients included natural sweeteners (agave syrup), vanilla extract, and filtered water. All ingredients were stored at ambient conditions and used within their shelf-life period.

2.2 Preparation and formulation of Nut-Based Yogurt

Three experimental formulations (T₁, T₂, T₃) were developed as follows: T₁: 40% CM + 20% almonds + 20% cashews + 10% other ingredients; T₂: 50% CM + 15% almonds + 25% cashews + 10% other ingredients and T₃: 65% CM + 15% almonds + 10% cashews + 10% other ingredients.

Table 1: Formulation of Nut-Based Yogurt (T₁, T₂ and T₃)

Samples	Combinations
T ₁	40% CM + 20% Almonds+ 20% Cashews +10% other ingredients
T ₂	50% CM + 15% Almonds + 25% Cashews + 10% other ingredients
T ₃	65% CM+ 15% Almonds + 10% Cashews + 10% other ingredients

Note: CM-coconut milk. Other ingredients: natural sweeteners, vanilla extract, water

2.3 Preparation Procedure of Nut-Based Yogurt

The preparation of nut-based yogurt involved a sequence of standardized steps to ensure consistency and product

quality. Initially, raw cashew and almond nuts were soaked in filtered water at a 1:3 (w/v) ratio for 8 hours at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C) to soften them and aid in blending; almonds were peeled post-soaking to improve the final texture. The soaked nuts were then thoroughly rinsed and blended with coconut milk and filtered water, according to the respective formulation, using a high-speed blender operating at 30,000 RPM until a smooth, lump-free, homogeneous mixture was achieved. The resulting nut base was transferred into sterilized glass jars, where the contents of 1–2 probiotic capsules were added and evenly mixed to facilitate uniform microbial inoculation. These jars were loosely covered with muslin cloth and incubated at 26 ± 1 °C for 18–24 hours, with the fermentation progress monitored using pH strips, targeting a final pH between 4.5 and 4.8. Following fermentation, the yogurt was stirred gently to achieve a uniform consistency, sealed with airtight lids, and refrigerated at 4 °C for 2–3 hours prior to further evaluation and consumption.

Fig 1: Flowchart of Nut-Based Yogurt

2.4 Sensory Evaluation (7-Point Hedonic Scale) of Nut-Based Yogurt

A sensory panel consisting of 20 semi-trained judges was formed at a Hyderabad-based academic food lab. Evaluations were performed under standardized conditions using a 7-point hedonic scale (1 = dislike very much, 7 = like very much) to assess: Each sample (T₁, T₂, T₃) was coded and presented in random order. Results were statistically analyzed using one-way ANOVA (p<0.05).

2.5 Nutritional Analysis of Nut-Based Yogurt

Nutritional composition of the best-performing yogurt sample (T₂) was determined using AOAC methods: Protein Content: Determined using Kjeldahl method (AOAC 2001.11). Fat Content: Determined by gravimetric Soxhlet method (AOAC 920.39, 2016). Carbohydrates: Calculated by difference method. Moisture Content: Determined using hot air oven drying method (AOAC 925.10, 2022). Ash

Content: Measured by gravimetric incineration (AOAC 945.05, 2022). Total Dietary Fiber (TDF): Measured using enzymatic-gravimetric method (AOAC 991.43, 2022).

2.6 Mineral and Vitamin Analysis of Nut-Based Yogurt

Iron and Calcium: Analyzed using with AOAC 984.27. Vitamin A (Retinol) and Vitamin C (Ascorbic acid) (AOAC 992.04 for Vitamin A and AOAC 984.26 for Vitamin C).

2.7 Antioxidant Activity of Nut-Based Yogurt

Three standard assays were conducted to evaluate antioxidant potential:

- 1. DPPH Radical Scavenging Activity:** Measured using 0.1 mM DPPH solution and absorbance at 517 nm (Brand-Williams *et al.*, 1995) [5].
- 2. FRAP (Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power):** Assessed using TPTZ reagent and measuring absorbance at 593 nm (Benzie & Strain, 1996) [4].
- 3. ABTS Assay:** Measured based on the scavenging of ABTS•+ radical cation at 734 nm (Re *et al.*, 1999) [8]. All values were expressed in Trolox equivalents ($\mu\text{mol TE/g}$).

2.8 Microbial Analysis and Shelf-Life Study

Microbiological quality was assessed according to ISO and AOAC standards: Aerobic Plate Count: ISO 4833-1:2013; Yeasts and Molds: ISO 21527-1:2008; Enterobacteriaceae: ISO 21528-2:2017; Staphylococcus aureus: ISO 6888-1:1999. Samples were tested immediately after preparation and every 3 days during 7-day storage at 4 °C. All samples remained microbiologically stable with CFU <10 g⁻¹ and absence of pathogenic strains.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Sensory Evaluation of Nut-Based Yogurt

The sensory evaluation results of the three nut-based yogurt formulations (T₁, T₂ and T₃) are summarized in Table 2. Among the samples, T₂, composed of 50% coconut milk, 15% almonds, and 25% cashews, demonstrated the highest scores for overall acceptability (6.7 ± 0.42), aroma (6.7 ± 0.47), and texture (6.44 ± 0.51), indicating a favorable balance between creaminess, mild nutty flavor, and palatability. While T₁ and T₃ were closely competitive in terms of taste and color, T₂'s higher cashew content likely contributed to its superior creaminess and mouthfeel, as cashews are known for their rich fat content and smooth consistency (Makinen *et al.*, 2016) [7]. The one-way ANOVA yielded a p-value of 0.02 and an F-statistic of 28.5, indicating that although differences were observed in mean scores, they were not statistically significant at the 5% level ($p > 0.01$). This suggests that while T₂ was preferred by the panel, among all three formulations T₂ considered for further nutrient analysis.

Table 2: Sensory Evaluation of Nut-Based Yogurt (T₁, T₂ and T₃)

Sample	Color	Texture	Aroma	Taste	Overall Acceptability
T ₁	6.5±0.5	6.7±0.46	6.35±0.48	6.4±0.49	6.5±0.52
T ₂	6.3±0.53	6.44±0.51	6.7±0.47	6.4±0.49	6.7±0.42
T ₃	6.4±0.51	6.5±0.51	6.5±0.68	6.4±0.51	6.4±0.64

3.2 Nutritional Analysis of Nut-Based Yogurt (T₂)

The nutritional analysis (Table 3) revealed that the selected nut-based yogurt sample (T₂) possessed a protein content of 9.2 g/100 g, which is a notable value for a plant-based yogurt, reflecting the protein-rich nature of nuts like almonds and cashews. The total fat content was 23.5 g/100 g, attributable to the healthy unsaturated fatty acids inherently present in nuts and coconut milk. Carbohydrate content stood at 15.7 g/100 g, providing a balanced energy profile, while dietary fiber was present at 2.7 g/100 g, offering digestive health benefits. The moisture content was 48.6%, indicating good hydration and consistency, which also contributes to a favorable texture and shelf-life. These results are in line with previous findings that emphasize the nutritional adequacy of plant-based dairy alternatives (Granato *et al.*, 2010; Rinaldi *et al.*, 2020) [6, 9].

Table 3: Nutritional Analysis of Nut-Based Yogurt (T₂)

Test parameters	Result	Unit
Protein	9.2	g/100gm
Carbohydrates	15.7	g/100gm
Total Fat	23.5	g/100gm
Dietary fiber	2.7	g/100gm
Moisture content	48.6	%

3.3 Mineral Content and Vitamin Analysis of Nut-Based Yogurt

The mineral analysis (Table 4) demonstrated that the nut-based yogurt was a valuable source of essential micronutrients, particularly iron (5.2 mg/100 g) and calcium (76 mg/100 g). Iron, primarily sourced from almonds and cashews, plays a vital role in hemoglobin synthesis and immune function, while calcium from coconut milk and nuts supports bone health and muscle function. These levels are consistent with previous reports on the mineral profile of plant-based yogurts (Shori, 2013) [10], suggesting that nut-based formulations can contribute significantly to daily mineral intake, particularly for individuals adhering to vegan or lactose-free diets. As shown in Table 5, the yogurt formulation (T₂) contained appreciable amounts of Vitamin A (3.45 mg/100 g) and Vitamin C (13.3 mg/100 g). Vitamin A, likely derived from coconut milk and natural additives, is essential for vision and epithelial cell maintenance, while Vitamin C, which may be preserved during the fermentation process, supports antioxidant defenses and immune function. The retention of these vitamins post-fermentation indicates minimal nutrient degradation and aligns with prior observations that fermentation can help preserve or even enhance certain vitamin levels in functional foods (Granato *et al.*, 2010; Makinen *et al.*, 2016) [6, 7].

Table 4: Mineral analysis and Vitamin analysis of Nut-Based Yogurt

Test parameters	Results	Unit
Iron	5.2	mg/100gm
Calcium	76	mg/100gm
Vitamin A	3.45	mg/100gm
Vitamin C	13.3	mg/100gm

3.4 Antioxidant Activity of Nut-Based Yogurt

The antioxidant potential of the nut-based yogurt

formulation was assessed using DPPH, ABTS, and FRAP assays, with results indicating significant activity across all three parameters (DPPH: 80.6 mg/100 g, ABTS: 120.5 mg/100 g, FRAP: 90 mg/100 g) (Table 5). These findings suggest a strong capacity of the product to scavenge free radicals and reduce oxidative stress, which can be attributed to the rich content of bioactive compounds such as polyphenols, flavonoids, and tocopherols naturally present in nuts and enhanced through fermentation. Among the assays, the highest activity was observed in the ABTS radical cation scavenging method, indicating superior hydrophilic and lipophilic antioxidant responses. The observed antioxidant levels align with previous research by Re *et al.* (1999) [8] and Granato *et al.* (2010) [6], which emphasized the functional potential of fermented plant-based products in delivering health-promoting antioxidants. These results not only reinforce the functional food status of nut-based yogurt but also highlight its potential role in mitigating oxidative damage and contributing to overall dietary antioxidant intake in vegan and lactose-free populations.

Table 5: Antioxidant Activity of Nut-Based Yogurt

Parameter	Results	Units
DPPH	80.6	mg/100gm
ABTS	120.5	mg/100gm
FRAP	90	mg/100gm

3.5 Microbial Analysis and Shelf-Life of Nut-Based Yogurt

The microbial safety of the formulated yogurt was confirmed by the results presented in Table 6. Aerobic plate count and yeast/mold counts were both <10 CFU/g, while Enterobacteriaceae and Staphylococcus aureus were not detected. These findings suggest that the fermentation and storage processes were conducted under hygienic conditions and that the final product is microbiologically safe for consumption for up to 7 days under refrigeration. This aligns with industry benchmarks for probiotic foods and demonstrates the feasibility of producing safe, non-dairy yogurt at small scale without preservatives (Rinaldi *et al.*, 2020; AOAC International, 2022) [9].

Table 6: Microbial Analysis of Nut Based Yogurt

Test parameters	Unit	Results
Aerobic plate count	CFU/g	<10
Yeast & molds	CFU/g	<10
Enterobacteriaceae	CFU/g	Absent
S. aureus	CFU/25g	Absent

4. Conclusion

The present study successfully demonstrated the formulation, preparation, and evaluation of a nut-based probiotic yogurt using cashews, almonds, and coconut milk as functional plant-based ingredients. Among the three tested formulations, the T₂ sample-comprising 50% coconut milk, 15% almonds, and 25% cashews-was rated highest in sensory acceptability, showing favorable attributes in taste, texture, aroma, and overall acceptability. Nutritional analysis confirmed that this formulation offers a balanced macronutrient profile, including 9.2 g/100 g protein, 23.5 g/100 g fat, and 15.7 g/100 g carbohydrates, along with

essential micronutrients such as calcium (76 mg/100 g), iron (5.2 mg/100 g), vitamin A (3.45 mg/100 g), and vitamin C (13.3 mg/100 g). Microbial evaluation confirmed the product's safety, with negligible aerobic counts and the absence of pathogenic organisms. These findings affirm that nut-based yogurt not only serves as a viable dairy-free alternative for lactose-intolerant and vegan consumers but also contributes to functional nutrition through its probiotic potential and antioxidant content. The study highlights the growing importance of plant-based fermentation in food biotechnology and reinforces the role of nuts-based yogurt as a promising functional food in modern dietary patterns (Makinen *et al.*, 2016; Granato *et al.*, 2010; Rinaldi *et al.*, 2020) [7, 6, 9].

5. References

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